

THE CULTURE OF THE INTERNAL AFFAIRS OFFICER IN COMMUNITY DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract. The article analyzes the problems related to the organization of the service of modern professional internal affairs as a result of the reforms carried out in the system of internal affairs bodies. At the same time, the significance of the Codex in the legal framework created in the development of the society, the moral and ethical qualities of the internal affairs officers, their attitude to their profession and responsibility is highlighted.

Keywords. Social order in the life of society, professionalization of internal affairs service, moral and moral image of the employee.

Introduction

Ensuring the stable socio-political, economic and spiritual development of the peoples of the world is difficult, and the UN adopted a number of international treaties and agreements, especially the "Sustainable Development-2030" (Johannasburg) program, to ensure stable security in the social life of the member states. At the same time, he recognized that the need for "police-patrol service" in maintaining public order to guarantee human rights and freedoms remains. At the same time, the proposal of the Uzbek government on the UN resolution "Enlightenment and religious tolerance" also gained the attention of the world community in terms of social development.

The world judicial system is establishing human rights and freedoms, social stability and security of civil relations, the growth of cyber crimes in the information society, the complexity of ensuring social order and security, and interstate cooperation in the fight against transnational organized crime. It implements training and professional development programs related to social order and sustainable security problems in the CIS countries. In this sense, the problems of ensuring social order and citizens' safety are being actively studied in our republic.

The problem of the professional and political culture of internal affairs officers in the development of society is compatible with important issues in the development of democratic institutions in society. In this sense, the economic and social reforms carried out in Uzbekistan are subordinated to the goals of "Human interest is the highest value", "People's consent" becoming the standard of activity of every civil servant, building a fair social state [5, p. 159]

Improvement of internal affairs system: problems and solutions

In the center of the Uzbekistan Action Strategy, socio-cultural development, ensuring a more nationalistic system of the judiciary and internal affairs service has become a three-pronged direction. There is an increasing need to increase the professional level of internal affairs officers in the perspective of the strategy of actions, to ensure the stability of social interaction and security, to develop not only legal, but also political thinking in the conditions of democratic freedom of the society. Therefore, the Codex of the Government of Uzbekistan on "Professional Culture and Discipline of Internal Affairs Officers" increases the political activity of citizens, and the emergence of public order and relations also requires the political thinking of internal affairs officers in their relations with citizens. In this case, the po The government of Uzbekistan carried out the reform of the internal affairs system in several stages with the renewal of relations between individuals, society and the state. According to our philosophical analysis, we believe that scientific-theoretical experiments in the process of maintaining public order and ensuring the rights and freedoms of citizens during the years of independence have prepared a certain ground for its first stage [3]. At the same time, we acknowledge that the first stage of reforms began in 2017. In statistical sources, 13 laws, 9 decrees, 40 decisions, 3 orders, 115 Government decisions, 167 interagency normative acts of the President of Uzbekistan were adopted.

First of all, in order to ensure the nationalism of the internal affairs service, the management system was seriously optimized, and the personnel were placed directly in the residential areas of the population, and the police bases serving 35-40 thousand residents were adapted to maintain order. At the same time, such police units began their activities in the public promenades, shopping centers. As a result, the quality level of the internal affairs service increased, ensuring the peace and tranquility of the citizens, and a positive change in the public's attitude towards the internal affairs service was achieved. This situation makes it possible to ensure a reliable state of the level of crime in relation to the increase of the population.

In the work of the internal affairs system, due to the changes in the work initiative of the employees, the change in their attitude to their duties, the dedication of the employees in maintaining social order due to the non-hiding of crimes, in the first half of 2021, 132 crimes were committed per 100,000 population. Due to the priority of ensuring security in the touristic potential and

attractiveness of Uzbekistan, the activities of special units against "safe tourism", "probation", and "cyber crime" have been launched.

The quality change of the internal affairs service ensured the effectiveness of the organization of crime and crime prevention directly in the population centers. Because, as an object of neighborhood administration, the activities of the prevention inspector were carried out to 9784 people, and on average it corresponded to 3.5 thousand people. Provision of 6787 service houses and cars was started to connect their activities with the life of the population. As a result, the preventive inspector was appointed as the deputy chairman of the neighborhood. 362 women's inspectors started working to protect the interests and rights of women in the internal affairs system. With the transition of the state to the local government system, control and accountability of internal affairs was also established [6].

An important aspect of the reforms in the internal affairs system was the introduction of proceedings based on the principle of "the inevitability of punishment for crime". For the fight against crimes, it can be considered as the application of an innovative method of establishing the mandatory audio-video recording of every procedural case, working with new approaches in criminalistics, remote interrogation and mobile investigative platforms. At the same time, it was determined that the arrival of every citizen in the internal affairs system and the full video recording of interrogations and inquiries. Due to the adoption of the law on combating cybercrime in the Republic of Uzbekistan, the activity of the internal affairs service, specialized in the areas of detection of new forms of crime, has modernized the quality of service. In this sense, we consider that some views on improving the work of the internal affairs system are controversial [6, p. 684].

With the transition of the internal affairs system to the principle of "Human interests are the highest value", the treatment of citizens in prisons was significantly liberalized, and the right to meet with a lawyer and the Ombudsman was granted without hindrance. In addition, they were equipped with more than 3,000 video surveillance cameras for their social protection. Four colonies, such as "Tashturma" and "Jasliq", which have passed their life, were stopped. Prisoners' civil rights have improved in the areas of voting, pensions, and social security, as well as vocational and medical assistance. By engaging them in production, 144 new shops were established for their social rehabilitation, and the creation of 4,896 new jobs for them strengthened their social status. We believe that an important event in the field, early pardoning of

4,973 convicts who truly regretted their actions, became a national tradition of humanism. lice system was based on the professional-political professional requirements of the employees.

A qualitatively new stage of the internal affairs service can be considered the 3-stage patrol service of the National Guard with public participation. As a result, 16 "Situation Centers" were established to maintain public order in residential areas, and more than 100,000 cameras and more than 8,000 operational call buttons were connected to the service of citizens at designated points. Due to the reforms of this period, it is important as a service that "in order to ensure safety in public places excluding the "human factor", the employees of the road patrol and post-patrol service are equipped with 6,100 "body cameras", 179 breathalyzers, and 6,514 tablets for recording legal issues." is important. Similar events were organized to ensure civil safety on highways. In order to provide the most convenient and efficient service to the population, services were organized in interactive ways. The requirements of car enthusiasts have also found a positive solution in terms of changing the color of the window, the procedure for obtaining car numbers. Issuance of ID cards and "biometric" documents of international standards to citizens eases problems related to foreign trips. Arming the internal affairs service with high-quality mobile communication and information communication technologies also enables innovative work.

As in any field, the activity of highly qualified professional staff, their moral and ethical image, and political maturity in the field of internal affairs ensure the honest and conscientious operation of the system. In this case, in the system of reforms, a new concept in the training of personnel was adopted in the Academy of the Ministry in the form of full-time and part-time education in 8 directions[4, p.23].

In conclusion, it can be said that in ensuring the integrity of the internal affairs system, high moral and ethical culture of the employees of the sector, honest and conscientious work in communication and relations with citizens, social groups and organizations, and demonstrating their high professional social image in front of the society are newly accepted. imposes the task of regulation with the code.

Secondly, it is appropriate to adopt the code as a program activity in order for internal affairs officers to vigilantly monitor events and incidents on the world political scene in their modern professional activities, to have high

political knowledge in maintaining public order, and to prevent religious and political offenses.

Thirdly, in the future, the activities of the internal affairs officers will be focused on cooperation in finding reasonable solutions to property and non-property relations of citizens based on sound innovative legal approaches to traditional activities.

Fourthly, it is important for police officers to have a good understanding of their duties and responsibilities, to get to know the socio-legal situation of the neighborhood and its citizens. The new policy of the state is not to punish the citizen, but to correct him socially actively, but it is planned to work on the principle of the inevitability of the punishment of the crime.

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